

Reportage of Environmental Issues in Northern Nigeria by Select Newspapers

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17259572>

Abstract

In today's world, artificial activities and natural disasters are putting the environment and its inhabitants at risk. Among the dangers experienced in Northern Nigeria are dryness and desertification, flooding, erosion, climate change and pollution. These adversely affect food security, health and socio-economic activities of the people in the country. As such, this study aimed to assess newspaper reportage of environmental issues in Northern Nigeria with the following objectives: To find the level of attention given to environmental issues in the select newspapers, to ascertain the environmental issues that are given more prominence by the newspapers and to analyse the frames used in reporting the environmental issues in the newspapers. The researchers employed content analysis, focusing on select newspapers from January 2011 to December 2020. The study was anchored on agenda-setting and framing theories. Findings showed that the level of attention given to environmental issues by all the newspapers is low and flood was the most prominent environmental issue reported by all the newspapers. The stories were framed mostly in the recommendation/solutions frame. The study concluded that despite the increase in environmental disasters across the north, the newspapers paid little attention to environmental issues and desertification and the most prominent environmental issue in Northern Nigeria, was not given much attention. The study recommended that journalists consider the socio-economic impact of environmental issues and use their agenda-setting role to frame environmental issues so that the public will feel their importance.

Keywords: Newspaper Reportage, Environmental Issues, *People's Daily, Daily Trust, Leadership, Northern Nigeria*

Introduction

One issue gaining attention in the global agenda today is the environment, which forms a significant part of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This includes mitigating pollution, access to clean water, sanitation and hygiene, clean air, marine conservation and energy. The changing weather conditions, as typified by rising temperatures and floods in some parts of the world, including Nigeria, have taken an alarming dimension. Flooding, erosion, oil spillage, and land and water pollution are just a few of these environmental issues that are felt across different geographical zones of the country. A report by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration -NASA- (2021) attributes

the hottest years to 2016 and 2020. The report outlines some phenomena caused by the rising temperature, such as loss of sea ice and ice sheets, mass sea level rise, more intense heat waves, and shifts in plant and animal habits.

The major environmental issue bedeviling the people of the north is desertification, which leads to drought and famine. According to Erunke (2021), fifteen (15) northern states and about forty (40) million people have been affected by desertification. Floods are another major environmental issue in the North, involving many people. Since June 2022, floods caused by heavy rains have swept through large swaths of land in twenty-eight out of the country's thirty-six states, including the FCT. The floods have affected 3.48 million people, resulting in many deaths and the destruction of over 637,000 hectares of cropland (WFP, 2022).

Saikia (2017) believes that one of the causes of the deep-rooted environmental problems in a country is a lack of awareness, which is the backbone behind inadequate management and utilisation of environmental resources. This study argues that environmental communication is one way to solve these problems. Environmental communication is intricately related to education and training activities, bridging complex technical know-how and soft action-oriented behavioural change among people (OECD, 1999). "Media are a central public arena through which we become aware of environmental issues and how they are addressed, contested, and perhaps resolved" (Maidunoma & Falmatami, 2018, p.341). The media is making an indispensable effort to sensitise the public about environmental issues. According to Ferdous & Khatoun (2020), print media is one of the most important means of communication as it plays a vital role in informing and educating the public through its in-depth news and analysis.

Media reports on the environment make people aware of the global environmental issues and their implications. Environmental issues have gained more attention in the past decade due to increased media coverage worldwide (Saikia, 2017). However, Ogadinma (2018) believes that the Nigerian media have not been handling environmental coverage in a manner commensurate with the attention it needs. Against this backdrop, this study aims to find out how newspapers frame environmental issues that affect the knowledge, attitude and practice of the people in northern Nigeria towards the environment.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the level of attention given to environmental issues in the select newspapers.
2. Determine the environmental issues given more prominence by the newspapers.
3. Ascertain the frames used in reporting the environmental issues in the newspapers.

Literature Review

Many studies have been carried out on the environment worldwide, but few have focused on environmental issues in Northern Nigeria. Some of the studies Nwabueze & Egbra (2016) content analysed two newspapers from Nigeria and Ghana to determine the coverage of climate change as an environmental issue for seven months. The significant

findings of the research centred on the environment as the major frame used in reporting climate change. It was also discovered that the media in both countries sourced their stories mainly from international fora.

Using content analysis, Ogundele & Sodeinde (2025) assessed climate change, content framing, and its implications for sustainability in Nigeria. Findings from the study indicate several sub-frames, some for adaptation, some for mitigation, one neutral sub-frame, and several that were employed as both mitigation and adaptation. Also, Ajaero *et al* (2024) analysed how newspapers in Nigeria and South Africa frame climate change issues, focusing on the adaptation and mitigation frames using content analysis method to examine the online editions of four newspapers; *Punch* and *Leadership* (Nigeria), and *Mail & Guardian* and *News Everyday* (South Africa)—over nine months (January–September 2018). Findings from the study revealed that *Mail & Guardian* (South Africa) published the most climate change stories (31.1%), followed by *Leadership* (Nigeria, 30%). *Punch* (Nigeria) had the least coverage (15.6%). The study concluded that African newspapers prioritise adaptation framing, aligning with the immediate needs of vulnerable communities.

Odoemelum & Hasan (2021) examined media framing of oil pollution in *The Guardian* and *Punch* newspapers in Nigeria. Findings from the study indicated that the selected newspapers used the reporting frames outlined by Semetko & Valkenburg (2000): responsibility, economic consequences, conflict, human interest and morality. The papers had a noticeable disparity in the frames as they silenced the responsibility and consequences frame, possibly due to ownership interest/ political economy. Also, Okorie (2024) aimed to determine the frequency of coverage, framing, and slant of environmental pollution in selected Nigerian newspapers (*Vanguard*, *The Punch* and *The Sun*), published from June to December 2023. The study found uneven coverage of environmental pollution, with *The Punch* providing the most extensive coverage and *The Sun* the least. Analysis showed no significant preference for any particular issue except for *Vanguard's* significant association with air pollution, though air pollution remained the least reported issue.

Emenyeonu *et al* (2023) explored the scarcity of media coverage on environmental issues in Nigeria, emphasising the need for innovative strategies and green cultural practices to mitigate environmental degradation. The authors adopt a qualitative methodology, relying on secondary data sources such as newspapers, journal articles and official environmental reports. The significant findings reveal an underrepresentation of environmental topics in Nigerian media, mainly due to poor funding, lack of trained environmental reporters and low interest in developmental journalism.

In another study, Obasi & Msughter (2023) investigated the level of attention given to environmental hazards in mining communities in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Using a questionnaire, interview, and content analysis, the researchers assessed 25 media practitioners, two radio stations, and four newspapers. Findings showed that the media were not involved in environmental campaigns; none of them had any program or column to address environmental challenges in the state. In contrast, Arikenbi *et.al* (2023) assessed "The Effectiveness of Mass Media Campaigns in Promoting Environmental

Sustainability in Nigeria." The study found that while mass media campaigns significantly raised environmental awareness, they had limited influence on actual sustainable practices.

Theoretical Review

Framing theory was adopted for this study to provide insight into why the media report issues using specific frames, make some issues salient, and downplay other issues.

Framing Theory

The concept of framing was first posited by Gregory Bateson in 1972. He defined psychological frames as a "spatial and temporary bounding of a set of interactive messages" (Bateson, 1972, p. 197) that operates as a form of metacommunication (Hallahan, 2008). According to Entman (1993), "to frame is to select some aspects of a perceived reality and make them more salient in a communicating text, in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation and/or treatment recommendation for the item described." In essence, framing theory suggests that how something is presented to the audience (called "the frame") influences the choices people make about how to process that information. Frames are abstractions that work to organise or structure message meaning. The most common use of frames is in terms of the frame that the news or media place on the information they convey. They are thought to influence the perception of the news by the audience; in this way, it could be construed as a form of second-level agenda-setting – they not only tell the audience what to think about (agenda-setting theory), but also how to think about that issue (second-level agenda setting, framing theory).

Framing focuses on how the media draws the public's eye to specific topics – setting the agenda. Then it takes a step further to create a frame through which the audience will comprehend such information. Creating frames for stories is commonly a mindful choice by sources, reporters, journalists, and/or editors. This justifies the media as gatekeepers who mindfully collect, select, "organise and present the ideas, events, and topics they cover" (Davie, 2011).

Methodology

This study employed the content analysis method. Newspaper articles were content analysed to get data for newspaper coverage of environmental issues using the coding sheet. The population of the study is 2,160 for each newspaper publication for 9 years (2011-2020). The total study population is, therefore, 6,480 editions. The entire population was studied, making it a census study. Data were gathered physically using seven research assistants (coders). Data were analysed systematically using SPSS and presented using tables and charts.

Results

Results from the content analysis of the three newspapers from 2011 to 2020 are presented in this section. Out of six thousand, four hundred and eighty (6,480) newspaper

editions from the three newspapers (*Daily Trust*, *Leadership* and *Peoples' Daily*) analysed, only two thousand and fifty-three (2,053) stories were reported on environmental issues spanning across flood, climate change, desertification, erosion and pollution. *Daily Trust* reported seven hundred and eighty-seven (787), *Leadership* had eight hundred and fifteen (815), while *Peoples' Daily* had four hundred and fifty-one (451) stories. The figure below presents the attention given to environmental issues by the newspapers under study.

Figure 1 shows that the *Leadership* newspaper had the highest (40%) stories on the environment. Again, the newspaper gave more attention to environmental stories in terms of page placement and story length.

Table 1 Statistical Computation on the Level of Attention

		Front	Inside	Back	Full	1/2	1/4	1/6
N	Valid	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		11.2000	52.3000	4.5000	12.3000	25.0000	16.0667	11.5667
Mode		11.00	17.00 ^a	3.00	7.00 ^a	22.00 ^a	14.00	4.00
Std. Dev.		5.89213	30.51416	3.30882	7.05716	11.64119	12.06286	11.61356
Variance		34.717	931.114	10.948	49.803	135.517	145.513	134.875
Min.		.00	10.00	.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	1.00
Max.		23.00	128.00	12.00	28.00	28.00	49.00	49.00
Sum		336.00	1569.00	135.00	369.00	750.00	482.00	347.00

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

The level of attention given to environmental issues was determined using page placement and story length. Table 1 above shows the statistical computations of the level of attention given to environmental issues by the newspapers combined. It shows that the highest mean of 52.300 was on the inside pages, followed by 25.000 (half size), followed by ¼ with a story length of 16.066, followed by full page with a mean of 12.300, and the least is 1/6 with the least mean of 11.566. In summary, among all the papers combined, the highest story length is ½ half-page reportage on environmental issues.

Table 2: Statistical Computation on Types of Environmental Issues reported by the Three Newspapers

		Flood	Climate change	Desertification	Erosion	Pollution
N	Valid	30	30	30	30	30
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		33.4667	15.5667	5.7333	4.1333	6.8667
Mode		27.00 ^a	7.00	2.00	1.00	4.00
Std. Dev		14.03624	14.78042	5.50820	4.06612	5.63079
Minimum		11.00	1.00	.00	.00	.00
Maximum		59.00	56.00	21.00	18.00	21.00
Sum		1004.00	467.00	172.00	124.00	206.00

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

The table (2) above shows that flood has the highest mean reportage of 33.466, followed by climate change with the second highest mean of 15.566, next is pollution with the third highest mean of 6.866, followed by desertification with the fourth highest mean of 5.7333, and last is erosion. In summary, for all the papers combined, flood is the environmental issue with the highest mean, while erosion comes last.

Table 3: Statistics on the Dominant Frames of Reportage by the Three Newspapers under study

		Problem definition	Causal Interpretation	Moral Evaluation/effect	Recommendation/ Solution
N	Valid	30	30	30	30
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		15.8667	6.6667	12.7333	30.1667
Mode		12.00	3.00	6.00	22.00
Std. Dev		8.88134	3.90696	10.94794	16.23127
Minimum		6.00	1.00	.00	5.00
Maximum		39.00	15.00	35.00	67.00
Sum		476.00	200.00	382.00	905.00

Based on frames for all the papers combined, recommendations/solutions have the highest mean of 30.16, followed by problem definition frame with a mean of 15.866, followed by moral evaluation/effect frame with a mean of 12.733 and the least frame is causal interpretation.

Comparative Analysis

Hypothesis One: No significant difference exists in the level of attention given to environmental issues in the selected newspapers.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Statistics on the Level of Attention given to Environmental Issues in the Select Newspapers

Level of Attention						
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remarks
Between Groups	29138.467	2	14569.233	3.560	.042	Significant difference exist
Within Groups	110493.400	27	4092.348			
Total	139631.867	29				

$P=0.042 < 0.05$, $F \text{ ratio} = 3.560 > 3.60 F \text{ critical at } df \ 2$

The table above shows a significant difference in the level of attention given to environmental issues in the selected newspapers. This is because the ANOVA table 4.4 above, the p-value of 0.042 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level, and its computed F ratio value of 3.560 is greater than the 3.00 F critical value at df 2. Consequently, the null hypothesis that no significant difference in the level of attention given to environmental issues in the selected newspapers is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the environmental issues given more prominence by the newspapers.

Table 5: ANOVA Statistics on Comparison of the difference in the Environmental Issues given more Prominence by the Newspapers

Environmental issues						
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remarks
Between Groups	7065.867	2	14569.233	3.524	.043	Significant difference exist
Within Groups	27065.500	27	1002.426			
Total	34131.367	29				

$P=0.043 < 0.05$, $F \text{ ratio} = 3.524 > 3.60 F \text{ critical at } df \ 2$

The table above shows a significant difference in the level of environmental issues or types of environmental issues in the selected newspapers. This is because in the ANOVA table 4.5 above, the p-value of 0.043 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level and its computed F ratio value of 3.524 is greater than the 3.00 F critical value at df 2. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the level of types of environmental issues given to environmental issues in the selected newspapers, is hereby rejected

Discussion of Findings

In answering research question one on the level of attention given to environmental issues in the select newspapers, the results in Fig. 1 show that most of the stories were placed in the inside pages of all the newspapers under review. Also, half a page was mainly used for the three papers' story length. Table 1 reveals a significant difference in

the level of attention given to environmental issues in the selected newspapers. The general level of attention given to environmental issues for the three papers is 156.600, 88.900 and 153.300 for *Daily Trust*, *People's Daily* and *Leadership* newspapers, respectively. This implies that *Daily Trust* has the highest mean attention, followed by *Leadership*, and the least is *Peoples Daily*, $P=0.042 < 0.05$, $F \text{ ratio} = 3.560 > 3.60$ ***F critical at df 2***. The general level of attention given to environmental issues by all the newspapers is low; this conforms with the findings of Ferdous & Khatoun (2020) who reported that the newspapers ignored important environmental issues and events, only reporting the aftermaths of incidents.

To determine the environmental issue given more prominence by the newspapers, the results in table 2 show that flood is the primary environmental issue reported by the three newspapers. *Leadership* gave the highest report with three hundred and forty stories. The least issue reported by all papers is erosion. Floods frequently occur, as journalists consistently report them, compared to silent issues like climate change and erosion. Also, significant differences exist in the type of environmental issues reported in the selected newspapers, where *Daily Trust* has the highest mean for types of environmental issues, followed by *Leadership* and the least is *Peoples Daily*, $P = 0.043 < 0.05$, $F \text{ ratio} = 3.524 > 3.60$ ***F critical at df 2***. In summary, for all the newspapers, floods are the environmental issue with the highest mean, while erosion comes last. Onobe (2017) also found floods to be a prominent issue reported by newspapers.

To ascertain the frames used in reporting the environmental issues in the newspapers, Table 3 shows that the recommendation/solutions frame has the highest mean of 30.16, followed by problem definition with a mean of 15.866, followed by moral evaluation/effect with a mean of 12.733, and the least frame is causal interpretation. In the table, *Daily Trust* has the highest number of reports using the recommendation frame, *Leadership* has the highest in terms of the definition frame and *Peoples' Daily* has the least representation for all frames.

Conclusion

The coverage of environmental issues by newspapers (*Daily Trust*, *Leadership* and *Peoples' Daily*) affects how readers assess these issues. Also, the way environmental issues are framed affects how the readers react to issues concerning the environment. During this study, it was found that the newspapers reviewed did not give adequate attention to environmental issues in Northern Nigeria. The most prevalent issue in the north is desertification and it was given the least attention compared to flood, pollution and climate change. This can affect how the people in the north view desertification and make decisions. The reports were framed following Entman's framing criteria, with 'treatment'/recommendation' frame predominantly the case more than the 'definition,' 'causal interpretation' and 'moral evaluation,' maybe because during environmental disasters, journalists and reporters alike tend to proffer solutions on how to avoid future occurrences. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. All the papers paid the least attention to environmental issues on their front pages, except on the inside pages; therefore, papers should promote environmental issues on their front or back pages.
2. All the papers had very few reports on desertification and erosion. It is highly suggested that these issues should be given more attention as their effects are also devastating.
3. Based on frames, all the papers lack causal interpretation in their reportage. There is a need to report issues using causal interpretation, as people would have more knowledge of issues when they know the causes and consequences.

Acknowledgements

This paper is part of a study sponsored by TETFUND/IBR with the number TETF/DR&D/UNI/ZARIA/IBR/2024/BATCH 8/22. We also acknowledge all those who have worked in the area whose studies inspired this study.

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